

Church Dynamics and Rural Development: The Case of the Baptist Churches in Romania

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ABSTRACT: Holistic development of a society can also be defined as the study of the relationships between urban and rural sociologic contexts. This paper asserts that one of the contemporary imbalances that exist in the Romanian society is related to the difference between fairly large urban setting and the rural one. This imbalance manifests itself both in social, economic, emotional and religious aspects. In general, Romanian village has been affected by all these changes that took place in Romania during the most recent years. Therefore, a holistic development of the national society would mean the narrowing of this gap through a combination between foreign investment in the villages and the existing resources provided by the inhabitants of the villages. As an intervening variable, this paper analyzes what the Church is able to do to support rural development. What should be done to change the dynamics of rural Churches? In answering these questions, this article focuses exclusively on the presence of Baptist Churches in rural areas, based on my own research and personal involvement. The article will also outline some of the most influential factors that affect the rural development; particularly the strategy for revitalization of the Baptist churches in order to bring a positive contribution to social rural development.

KEY WORDS: Rural Development, Church Dynamics, Baptist Church

General Factors That Influence Rural Development in Romania

What prompted the Romanian village to get in this situation not so good? We will reflect just a few of the main factors affecting rural society.

1) The Economic Factor

Limitation of jobs available and the lack of investors have made the rural economy to become very weak. This, he forced people to leave the countryside and move to the cities. The main source of income in rural areas was agriculture but lack of investors has been that it does not provide financial support to the population, so they were pointing toward cities.

The changing professional status of the rural areas observed after the 1990s forecasts that in the coming years there will be a shortage of employees, due to the reduction of industrial involvement to provide alternative sources of income. It is estimated only between 1996 and 2008 the number of employees decreased by almost 25%.¹ Out of 4 million people employed in rural areas registered in early 2008, only accounted for 1.56 million compared to 4.6 million urban employees. This substantial decrease of about 255 000 employed population segments (those who have the source of income) was caused, mainly, due to the increasing number of retired persons.

As after 1990, agriculture became the main source of income for rural inhabitants, this “job” was not fully borrowed and their descendants. Moreover, rural areas have been drained of manpower with the young and the most in the vast unable to continue engaging in agriculture. Socio-economic context is determined by economic power available to Romania.

2) Demographic Factor

Demography is the science that studies, using quantitative methods, the phenomena and processes on the numbers, geographical distribution, structure, density, movement of human population and its composition by age, gender. With the fall of the communist regime, it was possible to leave the country by Romanian

citizens finally in legal terms, which is why in recent years there has been a considerable decrease in population. Romania's population began to decline soon after 1990, when the gates were opened West.

On July 1, 2010, The National Statistical Institute estimated the existence of 20,294,683 Romanian population and density of 89.9 inhabitants per km². Central Commission for population and housing census, issued in a press release dated August 24, 2012, preliminary results on census population estimates that the number of resident population is 19,043,767, of which 9,764,011 women². Because there are margins of error for such statistics, the results are approximate but show that Romania is continuously decreasing population. The main factor in population decline is emigration to other countries. Because the migration flow is in constant development, it is very difficult to estimate the number of Romanian leaving the country, but their number is estimated somewhere around two or three million.

In terms of distribution in the territory, the Romanians have a more pronounced level of rurality. Rural settlements are less populated and smaller scale as an alternative to urban settlements. Last Statistical Yearbook 2010 shows that approximately 55% of the population lived in urban areas, and census results show that the urban population dropped to 52.8%³. The statistics show that people are moving towards cities or at least around them.

3) The Internal Migration Factor

Regarding internal migration between the 70s and 90s, it was the predominant direction from rural areas to urban areas. Since 1992 the number of those who have moved from rural areas (villages) in urban centers (cities) began to decline and mobility in the opposite direction (from urban areas to rural areas) increased, which was mainly due to as economic transition and declining work opportunities in cities.

After 1997 migration from rural to urban areas has exceeded the number of those who have moved from rural to urban centers, which partially is due to the phenomenon of urbanization.⁴

Sociologist Mircea Kivu in a brief interview to a magazine newspaper said that "the most surprising news of the preliminary results of census 2011 trend reversal evolution ratio population

urban—rural population.”⁵ (Internal migration, people moving from urban areas in rural areas.) Due to urban-rural migration, to be treated with seriousness church work in rural areas receive special attention. The number of those who move to areas adjacent to cities has greatly increased in recent years, and if it is a time to be addressed more serious activity of the Church in Romania in rural areas, now is the time.

Church Revitalization and Rural Development

1) Select Visionary, Competent and Dedicated Leadership!

Church ministers must be *actively involved in church life* even if serving in churches in rural areas. For this reason, “it takes a big man to lead a small church.”⁶ The leader plays an important role throughout this strategy, because he is the person to whom all will head to look in the process towards him they will be forwarded problems and he will have to have answers. John Brown, in the nineteenth century by one of his students wrote a letter that had just been ordained leading a small congregation:

I know the vanity of your heart and that you will feel frustrated that your congregation is probably very small compared to other congregations around you; but believe an old words that tell you when Jesus Christ will come in before His judgment throne, it will appear to have been too much.⁷

This active involvement of the church leader can be achieved if He *compassionate and ready to be sacrificed for the Church* that he leads. It requires selflessness from him to put community interests outweigh the interests of his own. In the process of revitalization, the leader must understand very clearly the place it occupies in this process. Leaving aside the fact that some leaders have lowered standards should always and always to be staring at the great men who have led the people of God, culminating in Jesus Christ. It is true that leaders must do everything as unto the Lord, but this does make it very professionally. There can be no perfect, but God’s work

no place for people who do not know Him. Too often the work was understood as a job and things took a strange turn.

The leader must have a *clear vision*, the latter meaning not only to have some ideas for church, and he must share God's given vision toward the Church. Leadership is responsibility of what God has provided and not the least responsibility for what leader received. Studies show that church models that have experienced revitalization and growth worldwide are those that the leader and the church got passion and vision, as the two most important elements that people have been attracted to Christ⁸. However in the process, there is a danger that the vision offered by God to be confused with their own desires and their own prospects. Because of this risk, the vision of God has some specific elements:

- * God offers the vision; He is the initiator.
- * No vision should not go beyond the God's intended purpose for church.
- * Fulfilling the vision God through His people.
- * Vision is God's will for that particular church and not a personal opinion of the church leadership.

2) Recognize the Need for Change and Get Involved in This Change!

It is not recommended to start the revitalization process unless there is clear and strong conviction that there is need for a change. The change also must start for further servant heart can partake with others change it. If someone wants rededication, there must be special in his life when rededication to God and to the church. The difficulty will arise when someone tries to be something it is not. Rededication to God is shown in the fact that our trust in Him grows. Faith in God is the engine by which we believe that everything is made of Him and through Him. This aspect of confidence in offering God can also be used in the right confidence that leaders must have in God's plan and vision he has for them.

Besides the dedication to God, people must recommit to the work of God, and this means to use their spiritual gifts received from Him. God decides what is best for believers and He decide the

spiritual gifts shared for each believer. The right man in the right place seems to be an appropriate way to illustrate how important it is for everyone to serve where God has placed him. Generally, when Christians serve in their spiritual endowment, they act less by their own strength and more by the power of Holy⁹. Christian Schwarz says that “the reason this is particularly important because it is the only way reform applies phrase ‘priesthood of all believers’”, and he presents a survey among 1,600 active Christians, German-speaking Europe, „shows that 80% they do not know their spiritual gifts”¹⁰. The survey is creepy, but perhaps this is true for many of the faithful Baptists in rural Romania. The church should create different ministries in which they engage, in order that believers to use their spiritual gifts.

In the process, members of the church are called to be devoted to the cause, not active participants and critical observers. Mark Dever said that “temple has many bricks, a flock has many sheep, a vine has many branches, one body has many members.”¹¹ Each member of the Body of Christ must fulfill his job.

3) Use Resources That Already Exist in Rural Churches!

Even if there are few resources in rural churches they need them to be exploited to the full. Churches rural tragedy is that often lack the “youthful energy” to call it. Most young people and young families go to big cities to aim for a better future. First, it must use the resources that are handy. To be asked for help, everything can be used for dynamic Church. Even if we speak of older brothers or older sisters, they may be useful in God’s house. Secondly, resources are closer than they appear to be. Human eyes see things stately mostly the smaller ones do not notice them. Napoleon Hill was a famous American author of motivational books and literature among other things, he says, “if you can not do great things, do small things in a great way”¹². Also Apostle Paul says “for consider your calling, brethren, that there were not many wise according to the flesh, not many mighty, not many noble; but God has chosen the foolish things of the world to shame the wise, and God has chosen the weak things of the world to shame the things which are strong” (1 Corinthians 1:26–27). There are several small churches potential resources that

may have or have them but not use them to produce spiritual revival and social impact. These are:

- * Sharing experiences with God.
- * Studying the Word for encouragement.
- * Personal and Community Prayer
- * Close relations with each other
- * Used to work hard

There are certainly elements that hinder development of the church, but focus on the positive aspects can bring church where it is.

4) Cooperate and Receive Support From Other Churches!

There are situations where churches are lacking servants. While it is a fact hard to accept for some, however, they are not lost hopes. One of the best ways a rural church can be revived is the support of other churches, usually larger. Winnings can be for both sides. In order to achieve this partnership every church must understand the need you have the other. A concrete example of this right connections and collaborations is the attitude that the Church of Corinth has for Christians Macedonia (1 Corinthians 8). Then it indicates the strategy missionary apostles, who were trying to send people consecrated for service every newly planted church.

Another dimension of this collaboration is partnering with other churches in rural areas. In this sense, refers not only to support large churches that have an important role in this process, but also to the cooperation between them small churches in rural areas. There are several reasons for collaboration with churches in rural areas is important:

- * support in prayer and spiritual and emotional support.
- * support material according to the needs encountered.
- * support for service personnel and active involvement.
- * maintaining the Church's witness.
 - * engage in service to young people and others who want the opportunity to serve.

Conclusion

The Church can contribute to social development in rural areas only to the extent that it would change its state, if it changes its dynamics. However it is quite difficult for some Christians to understand the importance of social involvement and understanding that all Christians are called to do this. Through the involvement of Christians in society, the world can acquire another situation, people change their evil impulses. Darrow L. Miller, try to capture this idea of active involvement in global discipling people urging the sense of conscience. He says, “the earth is the representation of what is in our hearts and minds. If the mind is dull, the world will be barren. If our hearts are hardened, our world will be a tough one”¹³. Social involvement with the proclamation of Christian values orientation can change places, cities, countries, nations and probably worldwide.

The church relevant in rural areas is the responsible social context relevant area of evangelism strategies. The model effectively Church is represented by affirming vision of each member. Thus, challenges need to be identified and they should be given clear answers to that then can be defined a strategy for church growth. Socially, it is important for the church to be involved to receive people’s attention and thereby building relationships.

NOTES

¹ Flavius Mihalache & Alin Croitoru, *Mediul rural românesc: evoluții și involuții* (București: Editura Expert, 2011), 55.

² Cf http://www.insse.ro/cms/files/statistici/comunicate/alte/2012/RPL_rezultate%20preliminare.pdf, (Last accessed November 13, 2016).

³ Cf. http://www.recensamantromania.ro/wp-content/uploads/2013/07/REZULTATE-DEFINITIVE-RPL_2011.pdf, (Last accessed November 13, 2016.)

⁴ <http://ec.europa.eu/social/BlobServlet?docId=8835&langId=ro>, (Last accessed November 13, 2016).

⁵ <http://www.hotnews.ro/stiri-11403176-.htm?nomobile>, (Last accessed November 13, 2016).

⁶ Paul W. Powell, *Shepherding the Sheep in Smaller Churches* (Dallas: Annuity Board Press, 1995), 23.

⁷ Mark Dever, *Ce este o Biserică sănătoasă?* (Oradea: Editura Făclia, 2009), 38.

⁸ *Ibid.*, 26.

⁹ Christian A. Schwarz, *Dezvoltarea naturală a Bisericii* (Timișoara: Editura Impact Media, 2003), 23.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 24.

¹¹ Dever, 109.

¹² Cf. <http://www.citatepedia.ro/index.php?id=64518> (Last accessed November 13, 2016).

¹³ Darrow L. Miller, *Ucenicia națiunilor* (Cluj: Editura Logos, 2001), 236.